

Influence of deposition strategy on the microstructure of volumetric WADED-fabricated AZ61 magnesium alloy components

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of various deposition strategies on the microstructure of volumetric components fabricated from AZ61 magnesium alloy using Wire Arc Direct Energy Deposition (WADED), also referred to as Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM). Because coarse grains can significantly reduce mechanical performance, thermal simulations were performed to identify low-cooling-rate regions associated with different deposition trajectories. Three deposition strategies were analysed: ZigZag, Spiral, and S-pattern. The simulated thermal profiles were validated by optical grain size analysis and hardness measurements. Among the tested trajectories, the S-pattern produced the finest microstructure, exhibiting the smallest average grain size in the critical zone and the narrowest grain size and hardness distribution. Additionally, its geometrical accuracy was well maintained, indicating that this deposition strategy offers a promising route for producing high-quality magnesium alloy components via WADED.

1. Introduction:

Magnesium alloys have attracted growing attention due to the increasing demand for lightweight structural materials [1,2] Magnesium is characterised by its low density, high specific strength, high specific stiffness, and excellent castability. Due to this unique combination of properties, magnesium alloys are widely utilised in the automotive, aerospace, and space industries [1,3–8]. However, their hexagonal close-packed (HCP) crystal structure provides only a limited number of slip systems, resulting in poor formability at room temperature [1,2,7,9].

Among magnesium alloys, Mg–Al–Zn systems (AZ series) are the most widely used [10]. The AZ61 magnesium alloy, containing 6 wt.% aluminium and 1 wt.% zinc, is a representative alloy whose mechanical properties are strongly influenced by grain size and the presence of precipitates. Alloys with finer grains exhibit higher tensile strength, hardness, and elongation, while tensile strength can be approximated from hardness [11]. A commonly used simplified relationship for this approximation is $\sigma = H/0.3$ [12]. Grain refinement can be achieved through higher cooling rates, whereas the volume fraction of precipitates depends on alloying content, cooling rate, and subsequent heat treatment [3].

Due to the limited formability of magnesium, casting is commonly used for producing semi-finished products. However, casting often leads to defects such as porosity, cracking, and coarse grains [1,2,13]. Among various casting methods, high-pressure die casting (HPDC) is the most suitable for magnesium alloys, as it provides extremely high cooling rates that produce finer grain structures and improved mechanical properties [14].

Additive manufacturing (AM) offers an alternative approach to casting, providing high cooling rates and enabling refined microstructures along with design flexibility [2,15]. Metal additive manufacturing (MAM) encompasses several techniques, including powder bed fusion (PBF), direct energy deposition

(DED), sheet lamination, and friction stir deposition [7,16]. One promising DED-based process is Wire Arc Direct Energy Deposition (WADED) [1]. However, the additive manufacturing of magnesium alloys remains challenging due to their low melting and boiling points combined with high reactivity, which often leads to defect formation [8,9,17,18]. These defects can be mitigated by optimising process parameters and employing suitable welding modes. The Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) variant of WADED, a modified form of MIG welding, reduces heat input by approximately 33% and therefore represents the most appropriate option [6,16].

WADED-manufactured parts typically consist of thin-walled and volumetric sections. Thin-walled parts are formed from single-weld deposits, whereas volumetric parts are constructed from multiple adjacent beads. To achieve sufficient fusion between neighbouring deposits, the overlap distance must be adequately defined, for which several models have been proposed [19,20]. The Flat-Top Overlapping Model (FOM) assumes that overlapping regions fill the valleys between adjacent deposits, resulting in a flat surface [19]. In contrast, the Tangent Overlapping Model (TOM) does not assume a flat surface but rather calculates adjacent beads with tangent edges, providing superior geometrical accuracy [20].

Various deposition strategies can be employed for volumetric WADED parts, including Raster, ZigZag (Meander), Contour, and Contour + ZigZag trajectories [21]. Because the start and end points of weld deposits often exhibit poor geometrical accuracy [22], continuous trajectories, such as Spiral or ZigZag, are preferred to minimise surface irregularities. Different strategies influence both geometrical accuracy and thermal distribution [21].

Deposition patterns also affect heat accumulation, which can reduce cooling rates and lead to casting-like defects. The recently introduced S-pattern trajectory was designed to improve thermal uniformity during deposition [23]. Comparisons among ZigZag, Spiral, and S-pattern strategies demonstrated that the S-pattern provides the most uniform thermal distribution, followed by Spiral and ZigZag [24]. Grain size analysis of Al-4046 deposits revealed large, elongated grains in the coarse-grain regions for the ZigZag and Spiral paths. In contrast, the S-pattern resulted in more equiaxed morphologies and fewer coarse grains [21].

Although Köhler et al. (2021) [21] identified the S-pattern trajectory as the most effective in terms of thermal distribution, the microstructural analysis was performed only at a single sample location. To accurately determine the grain size range, critical zones of each trajectory must be identified. This concept is further supported by FEM-based maximum temperature maps reported in the same work [21]. To accurately assess these zones, cooling rate analysis is necessary, which can be performed using FEM simulations to identify regions with the lowest cooling rates.

This study focuses on evaluating deposition trajectories for the WADED fabrication of volumetric components made from AZ61 magnesium alloy. To enable WADED to serve as an alternative to conventional casting, it is essential to suppress pore formation and coarse-grain development. While porosity can be minimised by adjusting process parameters, achieving a homogeneous grain structure requires careful selection of the deposition strategy. In this work, FEM simulations are employed to identify critical zones with low cooling rates for each trajectory, followed by experimental grain size and hardness analyses to assess the impact of deposition strategy on microstructural refinement.

2. Materials and methods:

2.1 Materials and equipment:

To investigate the influence of deposition strategy on microstructure, specimens were prepared via Wire Arc Direct Energy Deposition (WADED). A Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) power source (Fronius TPS 3200 CMT) was integrated with a six-axis robotic arm (KUKA KR 60 HA), providing high positional repeatability and motion precision. The feedstock material was AZ61 magnesium alloy wire with a diameter of 1.6 mm, while an AZ91 alloy plate served as the substrate to ensure metallurgical

compatibility. Pure argon was used as the shielding gas at a flow rate of 20 l·min⁻¹ to prevent oxidation. The substrate was fixed to a temperature-controlled base plate to maintain consistent thermal conditions during the deposition process.

2.2 Process parameters

The process parameters used for fabricating volumetric samples were selected based on previous studies [25,26] and are listed in Table 1. These settings produced weld deposits with a wide and low geometry, resulting in a deposit width of 10.46 mm and height of 3.01 mm in this study. A single track was deposited using these parameters, and the input thermal power was calculated to be 1404.51 W based on the measured current and voltage, assuming a 100% thermal efficiency. The overlapping distances, D1 ($\approx 0.738w$) and D2 ($= 0.5w$), were determined using the Flat-Top Overlapping Model (FOM) [27] due to its simplicity and ease of application. Here, D1 represents the overlap between inner deposits, while D2 denotes the overlap at the edges of adjacent parallel patterns. All the deposit characteristics are listed in Table 1 Table 2. The resulting deposit geometry is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1 Process parameters

I_{boost}	$t_{I_{boost}}$	I_{sc_wait}	vd_{sc_wait}	I_{sc2}	Travel speed	Preheat temperature
[A]	[ms]	[A]	[m·min ⁻¹]	[A]	[mm·s ⁻¹]	[°C]
430	2,5	35	30	50	15	250

Table 2 Deposit characteristics for fabrication of volumetric parts

Thermal Power P	Deposit Width w	Deposit Height h	Overlapping distance D1	Overlapping distance D2
[W]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]
1404,51	10,46	3,01	6,97	5,23

Fig. 1 Deposit geometry for fabrication of volumetric parts

2.3 Deposition strategies:

Three deposition path strategies were selected for detailed analysis: the Zigzag pattern, which follows a linear back-and-forth scanning path (Fig. 2a); the Spiral pattern, consisting of a continuous outward spiral from the center (Fig. 2b); and the S-pattern, a hybrid raster method designed to periodically reverse and shift the path direction (Fig. 2c). Each deposition strategy covered a square build area of 45.34 ×

45.34 mm, with dimensions chosen based on the overlapping distance between deposits. The final height of each sample was 50 mm, built up in 20 successive layers. The inter-layer time delay was adjusted according to the top surface temperature. Specifically, each layer was allowed to cool to an interpass temperature of 250 °C, as measured using a thermal camera (Workswell WIC Industrial). To maintain geometrical precision, the trajectory was rotated by 180° for each successive layer, with the spiral pattern additionally changing the direction of rotation. After the manufacturing process, all samples were measured using an optical 3D scanner (ATOS Triple Scan III). The scanned data were processed in the GOM Inspect 2018 software to evaluate the geometry of fabricated volumetric samples.

Fig. 2 Deposition strategies for manufacturing of testing cubes a) ZigZag, b) Spiral, c) S-pattern

2.4 Thermal simulation

Thermal modelling was performed using Ansys 2025 R1 with the DED Process add-on to simulate temperature evolution during deposition. The simulation accounted for transient heat transfer, including temperature-dependent thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity. Based on the overlapping distance of inner deposits and the deposit height, the simulated deposit size was set to 7×3 mm. Thermal power input was derived from measurements taken during the fabrication of a single track. Other adjustable simulation parameters are listed in Table 3.

Table 3 Parameters for thermal simulation

Parameter	Unit	Selected value
Cluster Volume	mm^3	21
Material Deposition Rate	$\frac{mm^3}{s}$	315
Preheating Temperature	$^{\circ}C$	250
Thermal Power	W	1400
Ambient Temperature	$^{\circ}C$	22 $^{\circ}C$
Convection Coefficient	$\frac{W}{m^2 \cdot K}$	10

The top layer was selected for the simulation, as it allows the easiest access for subsequent sampling. To identify regions with a higher probability of thermal accumulation and grain coarsening, the

deposition area was divided into an 8×8 grid (Fig. 3). Cooling rates were evaluated for each grid cell, allowing for the precise detection of thermally critical regions most susceptible to microstructural degradation. The resulting cooling rate data were then used to select sampling locations and to compare the effectiveness of different deposition strategies in controlling heat accumulation.

Fig. 3 Map of the cells in a) ZigZag trajectory, b) Spiral trajectory, c) S-pattern trajectory

2.5 Simulation validation

The selected simulation parameters were validated by comparing simulated cooling rates with experimentally measured cooling behaviour during the deposition of a single-track deposit. Thermal imaging was used to record the cooling curve. From this data, the time required for the track to cool from the peak temperature to the preheat temperature level was determined. This experimentally measured cooling duration was then compared with the simulated cooling profile obtained under identical process conditions, including power input, preheat temperature, and environmental settings (Fig. 4). The close agreement between simulated and measured cooling rates confirmed the accuracy of the thermal model and its suitability for predicting heat distribution in more complex volumetric builds.

Fig. 4 Validation of the simulation

2.6 Metallography and microstructural analysis:

Multiple zones were analysed from each sample, including one located in the critical region of each deposition trajectory and several others in selected zones to validate the simulation results. Samples were sectioned with a material allowance of 1.7 mm for subsequent grinding and processing. The specimens were ground using SiC papers with grit sizes of 320, 600, 1000, 2500, and 4000, and then polished with colloidal silica on a grinding and polishing machine (SAPHIR 250 A2-ECO). The polished

surfaces were etched with acetic Picral solution for 50 seconds. Grain size analysis was always performed at the mid-height of the weld deposit.

Grain structures were examined using optical microscopy (KEYENCE VHX-6000). Due to the low visibility of grain boundaries, manual outlining of grains was performed prior to automatic grain size evaluation using ImageJ software. The average grain size was calculated as a weighted mean based on the measured grain areas.

2.7 Microhardness

Microhardness was evaluated in the same regions where grain size measurements were performed. The measurements were conducted using a Qness 60 A+ microhardness tester with a load of 0.1 kgf (HV0.1). For each region, ten individual indentations were made to ensure statistical reliability. The average hardness value for each zone was calculated from these measurements.

3. Results and discussion:

3.1 Simulation results:

Three important findings emerged from the thermal simulations of the deposition trajectories (1F, 2F, 3F). First, the cooling rate progressively decreased with the accumulation of deposited material (1F). Second, slower cooling rates were observed near the outer edges of the component (2F). Lastly, the corners of the deposition trajectories exhibited lower cooling rates compared to the straight sections (3F).

The heating of the base material can explain the progressive decrease in cooling rate (1F). As the volume of deposited material increased, the substrate temperature rose, leading to reduced cooling efficiency. Similar effects have been reported in thin-walled parts, where pronounced temperature gradients develop during deposition [28].

The slower cooling rate observed at the outer edges of the cube (2F) can be attributed to less effective heat dissipation caused by the absence of adjacent material (Fig. 5). A comparable phenomenon occurs in multi-layer deposition: the farther the deposition is from the substrate, the slower the cooling rate becomes due to the reduced heat conduction through surrounding material [29].

Fig. 5 Difference between cooling rates at the a)edge of the part, b)centre of the part

Lower cooling rates in the corners (3F) result from the overlapping thermal influence of multiple path directions, leading to localised heat accumulation. In addition to thermal effects, material build-up can also occur in the corners of the deposition trajectories [30]. Excessive deposition may further intensify heat accumulation; however, this aspect was not included in the present simulation.

Together, these three observations highlight the regions most susceptible to microstructural coarsening and emphasise the importance of trajectory design in controlling the thermal behaviour of WADED builds.

Critical zones with the lowest cooling rates were identified for each deposition strategy. All critical zones were consistent with the general trends described earlier. For clarity, only the critical regions and

representative zones that support the previously discussed findings are shown in the figures below (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Positions of critical zones in a) ZigZag, c) Spiral, e) S-pattern. Cooling rates of critical zones in b) ZigZag, d) Spiral, f) S-pattern

For the ZigZag trajectory, the critical zone was located near the end of the deposition path, at the outer edge and in the corner of the component (H8, Fig. 6a). Fig. 6a illustrates the regions with low cooling rates (H1, H7, and H8) and the zones where the cooling rate decreased progressively with material

accumulation (H3 and H5). Fig. 6b presents the corresponding cooling rates for these zones. Zone H1 exhibits a low cooling rate due to its position in the component corner. Zones H7 and H8 are located near the end of the trajectory, with H8 also situated in a corner, making it the most thermally critical region.

Similar to the ZigZag trajectory, the Spiral trajectory exhibited its most critical zone near the end of the deposition path, at the corner of the trajectory and the component itself (H8, Fig. 6c). A slightly less critical zone, G8 (Fig. 6c), is located adjacent to H8. For comparison, the cooling rate of zone G7 is also shown in Fig. 6d. This zone is positioned at the corner of the trajectory but not at the outer edge of the cube, and it lies farther from the end of the path. To further compare the thermal behaviour of corner and straight path sections, zones G4 and H4 were analysed. As shown in Fig. 6d, the straight sections exhibited higher cooling rates than their corner equivalents, confirming that corners are more prone to thermal accumulation.

For the S-pattern trajectory, the lowest cooling rates were observed at the corners of the deposition path and along the outer edges of the cube (Fig. 6e,f). Accordingly, Fig. 6e,f highlights primarily these regions. Zones E6 and F6 were also included, as this area contains two consecutive path corners, which are expected to exhibit reduced cooling rates even though they are not located at the cube's edge.

The lowest cooling rates were found in cells A8, B8, F1, and H1. Zones F1 and B8 displayed similar cooling behaviour, including comparable reheating patterns (Fig. 6f). The rapid reheating immediately after deposition was the reason these cells were identified as critical. However, determining the precise location of the most critical zone is challenging for this trajectory type. A quantitative assessment of reheating effects would be required to clarify this behaviour, but such an analysis lies beyond the scope of this study.

3.2 Sample selection

Samples for grain size analysis were selected based on the results of thermal simulations conducted for each deposition strategy. For every trajectory type, one or more sampling locations were chosen to capture the regions exhibiting the most critical microstructure. Additional locations were analysed to validate the simulated identification of these critical zones.

For the ZigZag trajectory, sample Z1 represented the critical location (Fig. 7a). To verify finding 1F, samples Z2, Z3, and Z4 were analysed (Fig. 7a). To examine finding 2F, additional samples Z5, Z6, and Z7 were selected.

For the Spiral trajectory, sample O1 corresponded to the critical zone (Fig. 7b). To verify finding 3F, sample O2 was analysed. Because the thermal influence of the trajectory corner needs to be distinguished from that of the component edge, additional inner-path samples (G7 and G4) were included.

For the S-pattern trajectory, samples S1, S2, and S5 contained the predicted critical zones (Fig. 7c). Sample S3 was located in a region of thermal accumulation but not at the cube edge. Although simulations suggested that this zone was non-critical, it was nevertheless selected for verification.

Fig. 7 Selected samples of the a) ZigZag trajectory, b) Spiral trajectory, c) S-pattern trajectory

Sample S4 was selected to represent the condition where all three general findings from the simulations are simultaneously valid. Under these circumstances, samples S4, O2, and Z5 are located in regions with comparable theoretical cooling conditions. All three are positioned along the edge of the component, approximately 15 mm before the end of the deposition path, and on a straight section of the trajectory. The only variable among them is the thermal distribution characteristic of each deposition strategy.

3.3 Fabrication of volumetric samples

Three cubes were manufactured using the deposition strategies described in Fig. 2. Several geometrical inaccuracies were observed, both during the fabrication process and in the final parts.

The ZigZag trajectory exhibited the highest geometrical precision on the top surface (Fig. 8a,d). Minor deviations were observed at the segments corresponding to the start of the trajectories, which were slightly raised, and at the ends of the trajectories, which were slightly lowered.

The Spiral trajectory showed the poorest geometrical accuracy among the three cubes. Since the start of each layer coincided at the exact location, these regions were significantly raised (Fig. 8b,e). The ends of the trajectories were slightly lower, although the deviation was minimal.

The S-pattern trajectory demonstrated acceptable geometrical precision. The start points were raised slightly less than in the ZigZag trajectory (Fig. 8c,f). The main limitation in terms of precision was observed along the sides of the part, where the trajectory turns from the edge toward the middle of the component.

Fig. 8 Cube creted with a) ZigZag trajectory, b) Spiral trajectory, c) S-pattern trajectory, Geometrical deviations of the d) ZigZag trajectory, e) Spiral trajectory, f) S-pattern trajectory

3.4 Grain size comparison:

The microstructure analysis revealed Al–Mn and Mg–Al phases, which is consistent with the previous findings by Slavíček et al. [25]. Grain size was analysed at the centre of each weld deposit in the selected sampling locations (Fig. 9). ImageJ software was used to measure the area of individual grains. Grain diameters were then calculated based on the equivalent circular area. The average grain size for each region was determined using a weighted mean, with the weight corresponding to the measured grain area.

Fig. 9 Example of microstructure analysis

Grain size was analysed along each deposition trajectory following the procedure described above. For the ZigZag trajectory, the critical zone (G8, Fig. 10a) exhibited a grain size of 51.88 µm. No larger

providing comparable cooling conditions. The only varying parameter among these regions was the thermal distribution associated with each deposition strategy.

This comparison indicates that the S-pattern trajectory offers the most uniform thermal distribution, followed by the Spiral trajectory, while the ZigZag trajectory exhibits the least effective thermal control (Table 5). These observations are consistent with the analysis reported by Sun et al. (2021) [24].

Table 5 Evaluation of the grain sizes of various deposition strategies

	ZigZag	Spiral	S-pattern
Max. grain size	51.88 μm	60.27 μm	44,71 μm
Grain size range	26.46 – 51.88 μm	34.76 – 60.27 μm	26.32 – 44,71 μm
S4, O2, Z5	44.36 μm	39.75 μm	32.54 μm

The S-pattern trajectory exhibited the narrowest grain size range among all trajectories (Table 5). It should be noted that the selected zones were chosen to capture the most critical regions rather than to represent the full range of grain sizes; therefore, the reported range for the entire cube is purely illustrative.

The Spiral trajectory produced coarser grains than the ZigZag trajectory, despite its predicted thermal advantage. This discrepancy may result from local overheating within the Spiral strategy, although the overall thermal distribution was still better than that of the ZigZag trajectory. An alternative explanation could be an evaluation procedure error: the critical sample from the Spiral trajectory was extracted at a 45° angle relative to the deposition direction, which may have distorted the apparent grain size due to non-orthogonal viewing. This sampling angle was necessary to capture the location in the corner of the trajectory. It should also be noted that, although the Spiral sample was extracted from the exact critical zone, the ZigZag sample was taken adjacent to the critical zone due to spatial constraints on collecting multiple samples.

3.4 Microhardness comparison:

Microhardness measurement locations (Fig. 11) were selected to either validate the general findings from the simulations or to examine the critical zones of each deposition strategy. Ten indentations were made for each zone, and the average values and standard deviations are reported below (Table 6).

Fig. 11 Microhardness measurement locations of the a) ZigZag trajectory, b) Spiral trajectory, c) S-pattern trajectory

Table 6 Microhardness in selected locations

ZigZag		Spiral		S-pattern	
Position	HV	Position	HV	Position	HV
E1	66,04 ±2,47	H4	66,81 ±2,86	B7	63,58 ±3,41
E4	68,06 ±2,95	H8	64,54 ±3,28	C1	63,52 ±2,85
G2	69,39 ±5,35			F2	61,40 ±2,71
G4	66,95 ±3,22			H1	62,56 ±2,81
G6	67,19 ±3,52				
G8	65,22 ±2,99				

For the ZigZag trajectory, hardness decreased progressively along the trajectory (G2, G4, G6, G8), confirming finding 1F. Zone E1 exhibited lower hardness than zone E4, in agreement with finding 2F. In the Spiral trajectory, lower hardness was observed at the corners (H8) compared to the straight segments (H4), confirming finding 3F. Critical zones in both ZigZag and Spiral trajectories corresponded to the lowest hardness values.

In contrast, the S-pattern trajectory did not show a similar trend, as hardness values were relatively uniform across all analysed zones. This observation is consistent with the narrower grain size range observed for this trajectory. Any apparent deviations in the S-pattern critical zones may be attributed to measurement error when considering the limited variation in grain size.

A notable observation is the overall lower hardness of the S-pattern cube compared to the ZigZag and Spiral cubes. The three cubes were manufactured consecutively in the order ZigZag–Spiral–S-pattern, while all remained on the heating plate at 250 °C. Consequently, the ZigZag and Spiral cubes likely experienced considerable precipitation hardening. S. Coletto reported that AZ91 subjected to isothermal ageing at 250 °C exhibited a significant increase in hardness within just one hour (\approx approximately 10%) [31]. Since AZ61 has a composition similar to AZ91, a comparable behaviour can be expected. Therefore, comparisons of hardness were made only within each cube, rather than between cubes.

5. Conclusion:

This study demonstrated the significant influence of deposition path strategies on the microstructure of volumetric WADED components made from AZ61 magnesium alloy. Thermal simulations successfully predicted regions of thermal accumulation and low cooling rates, which were confirmed by optical grain size and microhardness measurements. The S-pattern trajectory yielded the finest and most uniform microstructure, characterised by the lowest maximum grain size (44.71 μm), the narrowest grain size range (26.32–44.71 μm), and effective thermal control, while maintaining acceptable geometrical accuracy. In contrast, the ZigZag trajectory offered superior geometrical precision but less consistent microstructural quality, and the Spiral trajectory generated the worst geometrical accuracy and the coarsest grains (60.27 μm). These findings demonstrate that careful trajectory design is a powerful tool for tailoring microstructure in WADED components. They provide a foundation for process-aware strategies in the additive manufacturing of lightweight structural parts.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo Repository at

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17506822>

The original version of the author's preprint of this study is openly available in the Zenodo Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17506854>

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Filip Seidler: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Methodology, Data curation. **Jakub Slavíček:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Daniel Koutný:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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